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Research Article

A Green Chemistry Approach to Thiazolidine-4-Carboxylic Acids: Design, Docking of Antiviral Activity

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ABSTRACT

Green chemistry principles advocate for the development of more sustainable synthetic methods by enhancing efficiency, minimizing toxic solvent usage, reducing reaction steps, and limiting chemical waste. In alignment with these principles, microwave-assisted synthesis was employed to rapidly construct a series of thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid derivatives, inspired by the structure of the natural amino acid cysteine. To evaluate their therapeutic potential, drug-likeness, and safety profiles, computational analyses were conducted, including molecular docking by using Pyrx software. The combined experimental and computational results provide a promising foundation for the development of these compounds as potential pharmacological agents. Further research is currently being conducted to determine the antiviral efficacy of these thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid derivatives.

INTRODUCTION

Green chemistry was first introduced in the 1990s and includes 12 principles. The green processes diminish the adverse effects of any chemical reaction by following certain criteria viz. catalyst- and solvent-free synthesis and designing of biodegradable and less toxic products with high efficiency. In this review article, we have compiled researches which step ahead toward green chemistry. In the past few years, divergent

synthetic strategies^[1] have been introduced aimed at efficient and green synthesis using inexpensive reactants, nontoxic solvents, reusable catalysts, nanoparticle-catalyzed synthesis, and solvent-free synthesis with high yields using different techniques such as microwave irradiation (MWI), sonochemistry, surface chemistry and others. Multicomponent reactions (MCRs) (Strecker, Ugi, Bucherer-Bergs, Biginelli) are excellent pathways for the synthesis of heterocycles^[2] as they have all the features for ideal synthesis like

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simple procedure for generating complex hybrid molecules in fewer steps which possess excellent pharmaceutical activity with high atom economy and eco-friendliness [3,4]. The notable features of thiazolidine scaffolds compel us to study the literature and outline the status of thiazolidine, its derivatives and their biological significance.

Microwave-assisted organic synthesis of various heterocyclic moieties is an effective and environment-friendly synthetic approach and becoming an effective tool of green chemistry method [5]. Microwave irradiation is an effective form of heating depends on the capacity of analogues to translate electromagnetic energy into heat [6]. L-cysteine contains not only nitrogen, which is found in all amino acids, but also sulfur in its molecular structure, and these elements serve as heteroatom dopants with appropriate energy levels to enhance the blue emission intensity [7,8]; therefore, we chose L-cysteine as a carbon source in this study. One of the most eminent heterocyclic motifs, thiazolidine, is a five-membered heterocycle system having the formula C_3H_7NS containing one nitrogen and one sulfur atom, and which exhibits notable medicinal and pharmaceutical properties. In the thiazolidine nucleus, many substitutions are possible on 2, 4 and 5 positions responsible for enhancing the compound's pharmaceutical importance. Thiazolidine and its composites are key components of many natural products and drugs and are also present in many synthetic compounds such as anticancer [9-12], antimicrobial [13-15], antitumor [16,17], antidiabetic [18], antiparasitic [19,20], anti-inflammatory [21-23], antitubercular [24], antifungal [25], antiviral [26,27], anti-HIV [28-30], cytotoxicity [31], antitrypanosomal [32], antinociceptive and anti-hypernociceptive compounds [33].

Computational methods are now an important component of modern drug discovery [34] PyRx includes a docking wizard. Specific aspects for using PyRx as well as consideration for data preparation docking and data analysis also describes. Drug discovery is attractive research area that enables application of cutting edges biomedical research to improve health of man people by active components of natural origin have been under enormous investigation as potential studies that were performed by using PyRx docking tool through autodock vina software [35].

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Computational Methodology

The computational workflow in this study involved four major stages: molecular design, novelty verification, protein selection, and docking preparation.

1. Molecular Design using ChemSketch software (ACD/Labs) was utilized to construct and visualize the chemical structures of the target molecules. The software was also employed to determine key physicochemical properties, including molecular weight, molecular formula, logP (partition coefficient), molar refractivity, hydrogen bond donors and acceptors, polar surface area, and structural geometry. This initial computational analysis provided insights into the drug-likeness and potential chemical behavior of the designed compounds.

2. Novelty Check and Data Retrieval from PubChem, an open-access chemical database maintained by the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), was used to verify the novelty of the designed molecules by cross-referencing them with existing chemical entries. This ensured that the compounds were

structurally unique. Additionally, PubChem provided information on the physicochemical nature, chemical classification, and reported biological activities of structurally similar molecules.

3. Protein Structure Selection from the Protein DataBank (PDB) was accessed to obtain three-dimensional crystal structures of relevant viral proteins. Specifically, PDB IDs 8EQS and 1XOE were selected based on their biological relevance, structural resolution, and availability of active site information. The structures were downloaded in .pdb format for subsequent docking studies.

8eqs

1xoe

4. Ligand and Protein Preparation using BIOVIA Discovery Studio: Visualizer was used to prepare the ligands and protein receptors for molecular docking. Designed ligands underwent energy minimization to achieve stable conformations. The protein structures were preprocessed by removing water molecules,

adding hydrogen atoms, correcting bond orders, and optimizing geometry. This preparation ensured that both ligand and receptor structures were in optimal form for accurate docking simulations.

5. PyRx Molecular Docking Steps

1. Install and Launch PyRx

- Download PyRx (latest stable version) from the official website.
- Install and open the software.
- The interface will have Molecule View, Vina Wizard, and other panels.

2. Prepare Ligands

1. Obtain ligand structures:
 - a. Download .sdf files from PubChem or draw them in ChemSketch and save as .sdf.
2. Convert to PDBQT:
 - a. In PyRx, click Open Ligand → select .sdf.
 - b. Right-click → *Convert to AutoDock Ligand (pdbqt)*.
3. Energy minimization:
 - a. In Molecule View, select the ligand.
 - b. Go to Tools → Minimize Energy.
 - c. Choose Force Field and run minimization.

3. Prepare Protein (Target)

1. Obtain protein structure:
 - a. Download .pdb file from RCSB PDB.
2. Clean the protein:
 - a. Remove water molecules and unwanted ligands using software like Discovery Studio.
3. Convert to pdbqt:
 - a. In PyRx, click Open Molecule → select .pdb.
 - b. Right-click → *Convert to AutoDock Macromolecule (pdbqt)*.

4. Set Docking Parameters

1. Switch to Vina Wizard.
2. Select Ligand and Macromolecule from dropdown menus.
3. Set Grid Box:
 - a. Click Grid Box → Adjust Center (X, Y, Z) and Dimensions to cover the binding site.
4. Keep other settings default unless optimization is needed.

5. Run Docking

- Click Run Vina.
- PyRx will dock each ligand to the target and display docking scores (binding affinities in kcal/mol).

6. View and Save Results

1. Check scores:
 - a. Lower (more negative) binding affinity values indicate better predicted binding.
2. Export docked poses:
 - a. Right-click results → *Save as PDBQT* or *Save as SDF* for visualization in PyMOL or Discovery Studio.

7. Post-Docking Analysis

- Visualize interactions (hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic contacts) in PyMOL, Chimera, or Discovery Studio.
- Compare docking scores with standard/reference drugs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Designed derivative of thiazolidine 4 carboxylic acid

COMPOUND	STURCTURE	IUPAC
DERI 1		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(4-sulfophenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 2		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(1 <i>H</i> -imidazol-2-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 3		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-[1-(pyrimidin-2-yl)-1 <i>H</i> -imidazol-2-yl]-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 4		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(1-benzyl-1 <i>H</i> -imidazol-4-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid

DERI 5		(4R)-2-(2-amino-6-oxo-1,6-dihydro-9H-purin-9-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 6		(4R)-2-[4-hydroxy-5-(hydroxymethyl) oxolan-2-yl]-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 7		(4R)-2-(1H-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 8		(4R)-2-[(1E)-6-methylhepta-1,5-dien-1-yl]-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 9		(4R)-2-(pyrrolidin-2-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 10		(4R)-2-(6-chloropyridin-3-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 11		(4R)-2-octyl-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 12		(4R)-2-(piperidin-4-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 13		(4R)-2-(3H-indol-5-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid

DERI 14		(4R)-2-(1H-1,3-benzimidazol-2-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 15		(4R)-2-(4,5-dihydro-1,3-oxazol-2-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 16		(4R)-2-{[2-(methylsulfanyl)phenyl]methyl}-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 17		(4R)-2-(2-hydroxy-5-iodophenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 18		(4R)-2-(2-cyclopentylethyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 19		(4R)-2-[4-(diethylamino)phenyl]-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 20		(4R)-2-(3-chloro-2-hydroxyphenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 21		(4R)-2-(4-tert-butyl-2-hydroxyphenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid

DERI 22		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(2-hydroxy-3-nitrophenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 23		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(5-phenylfuran-2-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 24		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(3-chloro-5-fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 25		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(3- <i>tert</i> -butyl-2,5-dihydroxyphenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 26		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-[4-(pyridin-2-yl)phenyl]-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 27		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(1-methyl-1 <i>H</i> -imidazol-2-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 28		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(5-methyl-1,2-oxazol-3-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 29		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(2,3,5,6-tetramethylphenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid

DERI 30		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-[1-(benzenesulfonyl)-1 <i>H</i> -pyrrol-2-yl]-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 31		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-[2-(methylsulfanyl)phenyl]-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 32		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(2-bromo-3-hydroxyphenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 33		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(3-bromo-5-chlorophenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 34		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(4-bromofuran-2-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 35		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-(4-chlorofuran-2-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 36		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-{4-[bis(2-chloroethyl)amino]phenyl}-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 37		(4 <i>R</i>)-2-{4-[bis(hydroxymethyl)amino]phenyl}-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid

DERI 38		(4R)-2-(5-sulfofuran-2-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 39		(4R)-2-(4-tert-butoxyphenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 40		(4R)-2-(1,2-dihydroacenaphthylen-5-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 41		(4R)-2-([2,2'-bithiophen]-5-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 42		(4R)-2-(2,4-dihydroxypyrimidin-5-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 43		(4R)-2-(3,5-dipropylphenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 44		(4R)-2-(5-chloro-2-hydroxyphenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 45		(4R)-2-(2-formylphenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 46		(4R)-2-(3-formylphenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid

DERI 47		(4R)-2-(4-formylphenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 48		(4R)-2-[3-carboxy-4-(pyridin-2-yl)phenyl]-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 49		(4R)-2-(3-methyl-5-sulfofuran-2-yl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid
DERI 50		(4R)-2-(2-hydroxy-3,5-dipropylphenyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid

Table 2: PYRX DOCKING SCORE BINDING AFFINITY

SR.NO	COMPOUND	8EQS	1XOE
1.	ACYCLOVIR	-6.8	-7.1
2.	OSELTAMIVIR	-6.2	-6.2
3.	AMANTADINE	-5.5	-5.8
4.	INDINAVIR	-10.8	-9.2
5.	RIBAVIRIN	-7.2	-6.7
6.	DERI 1	-7.5	-6.1
7.	DERI 2	-6.4	-5.7
8.	DERI 3	-7.6	-7.5
9.	DERI 4	-7.6	-6.8
10.	DERI 5	-8.5	-8
11.	DERI 6	-6.6	-5.8
12.	DERI 7	-6.6	-5.7
13.	DERI 8	-6.2	-5.2
14.	DERI 9	-6.5	-5.8
15.	DERI 10	-6.7	-5.9
16.	DERI 11	-5.1	-4.7
17.	DERI 12	-6.5	-5.6
18.	DERI 13	-7.1	-6.8
19.	DERI 14	-7.3	-6.8
20.	DERI 15	-6.4	-5.7
21.	DERI 16	-6.6	-5.6
22.	DERI 17	-7	-6.3
23.	DERI 18	-6.4	-5.7

24.	DERI 19	-6.6	-5.7
25.	DERI 20	-6.6	-6
26.	DERI 21	-7.1	-6.6
27.	DERI 22	-7.5	-6.4
28.	DERI 23	-7.2	-7.3
29.	DERI 24	-6.9	-6.6
30.	DERI 25	-7.3	-6.4
31.	DERI 26	-7.9	-6.9
32.	DERI 27	-6.4	-5.9
33.	DERI 28	-6.8	-6.3
34.	DERI 29	-7	-6.2
35.	DERI 30	-7.1	-7.7
36.	DERI 31	-6.6	-6.1
37.	DERI 32	-7.5	-6.6
38.	DERI 33	-6.7	-6.3
39.	DERI 34	-6.4	-5.6
40.	DERI 35	-6.5	-5.7
41.	DERI 36	-6.6	-5.7
42.	DERI 37	-7	-6.2
43.	DERI 38	-7	-6.3
44.	DERI 39	-7.1	-6.1
45.	DERI 40	-8	-7.5
46.	DERI 41	-6.9	-6
47.	DERI 42	-7.4	-7.1
48.	DERI 43	-6.8	-7.3
49.	DERI 44	-6.6	-6.5
50.	DERI 45	-7.4	-6.3
51.	DERI 46	-7.1	-6
52.	DERI 47	-7.4	-5.7
53.	DERI 48	-8.2	-6.8
54.	DERI 49	-7.4	-6.6
55.	DERI 50	-6.9	-6.6

Table 3: Ligand interaction and 2d structure of the docked molecules

COMPOUND	Ligand interaction	2d
Deri 1		
DERI 2		

DERI 3			
DERI 4			
DERI 5			
DERI 6			
DERI 7			
DERI 8			
DERI 9			

DERI 10			
DERI 11			
DERI 12			
DERI 13			
DERI 14			
DERI 15			
DERI 16			

DERI 17		
DERI 18		
DERI 19		
DERI 20		
DERI 21		
DERI 22		
DERI 23		

DERI 24				
DERI 25				
DERI 26				
DERI 27				
DERI 28				
DERI 29				
DERI 30				
DERI 31				

DERI 32		
DERI 33		
DERI 34		
DERI 35		
DERI 36		
DERI 37		
DERI 38		
DERI 39		
DERI 40		

DERI 41		
DERI 42		
DERI 43		
DERI 44		
DERI 45		
DERI 46		
DERI 47		
DERI 48		
DERI 49		

The molecular docking analysis using PyRx was performed for standard antiviral drugs and fifty designed derivatives (DERI 1–50) against two target proteins, 8EQS and 1XOE. The binding affinities (kcal/mol) are presented in Table 2.

Among the standard drugs, Indinavir exhibited the highest binding affinity towards both targets, recording -10.8 kcal/mol (8EQS) and -9.2 kcal/mol (1XOE). This was followed by Ribavirin (-7.2 , -6.7) and Acyclovir (-6.8 , -7.1). Oseltamivir and Amantadine showed comparatively lower affinities, with docking scores in the range of -5.5 to -6.2 kcal/mol.

Several derivatives demonstrated binding affinities comparable to or exceeding those of the standard drugs. Against 8EQS, the top-performing derivatives included DERI 5 (-8.5), DERI 40 (-8.0), DERI 48 (-8.2), and DERI 26 (-7.9), indicating strong potential for target inhibition. For 1XOE, DERI 30 (-7.7), DERI 42 (-7.1), DERI 43 (-7.3), and DERI 40 (-7.5) displayed notable affinities, rivaling or surpassing Acyclovir.

The differences in binding scores between the two proteins suggest that certain derivatives may exhibit target selectivity. For example, DERI 48 showed strong affinity for 8EQS but moderate interaction with 1XOE, while DERI 30 was more effective against 1XOE. This variation could be attributed to differences in the active site architecture, hydrophobicity, and hydrogen-bonding patterns of the two proteins.

CONCLUSION:

Overall, these docking results indicate that multiple derivatives, particularly DERI 5, DERI 40, DERI 48, and DERI 30, possess significant inhibitory potential. Their performance against both targets highlight their promise as lead compounds for further optimization. However, as docking results are predictive in nature, molecular dynamics simulations, ADMET profiling, and in vitro assays are necessary to validate these computational findings and assess their drug-likeness and biological activity.

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